

Adaptive Intra-Symbol SMSE Waveform Design Amidst Coexistent Primary Users

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Abstract—An analytic approach is presented for optimizing Spectrally Modulated, Spectrally Encoded (SMSE) waveforms using independent selection of *intra-symbol* (within a symbol) subcarrier power and modulation order. The SMSE framework is well-suited for cognition-based, software defined radio (SDR) applications. By exploiting statistical knowledge about the spectral and temporal behavior of interfering signals, the inherent SMSE framework flexibility is leveraged to substantially increase system throughput while limiting coexistent interference. Results for a coexistent scenario are provided in which the analytic optimization of the SMSE waveform is demonstrated in the presence of multiple Direct Sequence Spread Spectrum (DSSS) signals. The results reveal significant performance benefits that demonstrate the potential of the SMSE framework to dynamically adapt to changing environmental conditions—key functionality required for future SDR implementations.

I. INTRODUCTION

The ability to satisfy ever increasing demand for increased system capacity, lower bit error rate (BER), and more users is heavily dependent upon spectral constraints. While there is certain disparity among spectrum utilization estimates, with sources suggesting that 70% to 95% is inefficiently utilized [1]–[3], all agree there is much room for improvement and cognition-based, software defined radio (SDR) is one enabling technology for obtaining it.

Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing (OFDM) has been identified as a key technology for implementing spectrally efficient SDR [4]. Relative to traditional single carrier systems, OFDM achieves greater frequency agility using a spectral domain design process [5]. The complexity of these designs ranges from simple spectral notching (avoid spectral regions with high interference or poor channel gain) to theoretically optimal methods, such as water-filling, that

strive to achieve Shannon capacity [6], [7]. However, these methods generally suffer from either limited performance capability or unrealistic design constraints. Additional techniques provide subcarrier adaptability through either *inter-symbol* (symbol-to-symbol) or *intra-symbol* (within a symbol) variability. The inter-symbol class of signals, e.g., OFDM-based 802.11 [8], typically use fixed assignment of properties (modulation type, order, etc.) from a preset pool for all subcarriers within a given symbol. Signals using intra-symbol adaptability vary subcarrier properties within each symbol. This has been used in both wired [9]–[11] and wireless applications [12]–[15] that have predominantly used spectral design to maximize OFDM system throughput without due regard to coexistent system impact – greater design flexibility through independent selection of OFDM subcarrier features is required.

This work addresses *intra-symbol* variation of subcarrier power and modulation order using the SMSE framework. The SMSE framework embodies a broad class of OFDM-based waveforms and its applicability has been demonstrated for several OFDM variants [16]–[19]. Results here demonstrate potential performance gain through adaptive selection of SMSE subcarrier modulation parameters. In a coexistent environment with four Primary User (PU) DSSS systems, the SMSE system throughput (bits/second) is maximized while adhering to bit error rate (BER) constraints for both the SMSE and in-band PU systems. By adaptively selecting subcarrier power and modulation order for each of the N_f IFFT components, the SMSE system is able to generate a waveform based on the observed PU signal spectrum. Additionally, when the SMSE system accounts for the temporal behavior of PU DSSS signals, it is able to further increase its throughput while continuing to adhere to BER constraints for both systems.

II. SMSE ANALYTIC FRAMEWORK

The general SMSE framework specifies the transmitted waveform design for the k^{th} SMSE symbol using a specific collection of waveform design parameters, including: *coding*, $\mathbf{c} = [c_1, c_2, \dots, c_{N_f}]$, $c_i \in \mathbb{C}$, *data modulation*, $\mathbf{d} = [d_1, d_2, \dots, d_{N_f}]$, $d_i \in \mathbb{C}$, *windowing*, $\mathbf{w} = [w_1, w_2, \dots, w_{N_f}]$, $w_i \in \mathbb{C}$, and a phase-only *orthogonality* term, $\mathbf{o} = [o_1, o_2, \dots, o_{N_f}]$, $o_i \in \mathbb{C}$, $|o_i| = 1 \forall i$ [16], [17]. Collectively, these terms functionally incorporate various waveform design features that are commonly employed in communications. The intra-symbol frequency components used to generate each SMSE symbol are controlled by the *assignment*, $\mathbf{a} = [a_1, a_2, \dots, a_{N_f}]$, $a_i \in \{0, 1\}$, and *use*, $\mathbf{u} = [u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{N_f}]$, $u_i \in \{0, 1\}$ parameters, where zeros indicate there is no transmission at that particular frequency. The *assignment* parameter specifies available frequency bands, while the *use* parameter dictates which ones are actually used. Thus, \mathbf{u} is a subset of \mathbf{a} , $\mathbf{u} \subseteq \mathbf{a}$, such that only assigned carriers can be used.

The spectral representation of the k^{th} SMSE symbol is given by [16], [17]

$$\mathbf{s}_k = \mathbf{a} \odot \mathbf{u}_k \odot \mathbf{c} \odot \mathbf{d}_k \odot \mathbf{w} \odot \mathbf{o}_k, \quad (1)$$

where \odot denotes a Hadamard product. The m^{th} subcarrier component of \mathbf{s}_k is given as

$$\mathbf{s}_k[m] = a_m u_{m,k} c_m d_{m,k} w_m e^{j(\theta_{d_{m,k}} + \theta_{c_m} + \theta_{w_m} + \theta_{o_{m,k}})}, \quad (2)$$

where $m = 0, 1, \dots, N_f - 1$ is the subcarrier index number, there are N_f total subcarriers, and c_m , θ_{c_m} , $d_{m,k}$, $\theta_{d_{m,k}}$, w_m , θ_{w_m} and $\theta_{o_{m,k}}$ are corresponding magnitudes and phases of the design parameters. The framework in (2) is well-suited for optimization given that independent selection of intra-symbol subcarrier power and modulation type/order is enabled through the $u_{m,k}$ and $d_{m,k}$ design parameters, respectively.

III. SMSE WAVEFORM DESIGN

While the SMSE framework offers a unified means for describing OFDM-based waveforms using a compact parameter set, the selection of parameters of interest must be done intelligently. Hence, SMSE system performance is maximized subject to specific design constraints. For this work, the design imposed design constraints include: 1) Fixed total average SMSE power (summed across all subcarriers), 2) Fixed maximum SMSE BER limit (for

all subcarriers), and 3) Fixed maximum BER limit for each PU signal.

For demonstration purposes, the design is further constrained to operate with a predetermined set of N_f contiguous *assigned* frequencies. The *coding*, *windowing*, and *orthogonality* terms in (1) are equal to unity. The data modulations are selected independently from a set pool containing 4-QAM, 16-QAM, 64-QAM, or 256-QAM. Thus, the final design process involves optimal selection of *data modulation* (\mathbf{d}) and *frequency use* (\mathbf{u}) parameters. Specifically, within the overall goal of maximizing its average throughput, the SMSE system first selects which subcarriers will be used and which will go unused. For each subcarrier selected, the SMSE system then selects 1) the modulation order (4, 16, 64 or 256) and 2) power to be allocated. The spectral design constraints for the k^{th} SMSE symbol is expressed as:

$$\text{Max} \left\{ \sum_{m=0}^{N_f-1} \mathbf{s}_k[m] \text{ Bit Rate} \right\}, \quad (3)$$

such that

$$\sum_{m=0}^{N_f-1} \{\mathbf{s}_k[m] \text{ Power}\} \leq P_T, \quad (4)$$

$$\sum_{m=0}^{N_f-1} \{\mathbf{s}_k[m] \text{ Interference}\} \leq I_T, \quad (5)$$

where P_T is the total average SMSE symbol power limit and I_T is the maximum allowable interfering SMSE power that the PUs can tolerate and still maintain their BER limit.

If the spectral constraints in (3) through (5) are viewed *deterministically* with respect to the *current* subchannel response, they can be expressed as:

$$\text{Max}_{M_m = \left\{ \begin{smallmatrix} 1, 4, 16, \\ 64, 256 \end{smallmatrix} \right\}} \left\{ \sum_{m=0}^{N_f-1} \log_2(M_m) \right\}, \quad (6)$$

$$\sum_{m=1}^{N_f-1} P(M_m, H_m, S_m) \leq P_T, \quad (7)$$

$$\sum_{m=0}^{N_f-1} I(P(M_m, H_m, S_m)) \leq I_T, \quad (8)$$

where M_m is the m^{th} subcarrier modulation order, $P(M_m, H_m, S_m)$ is the required transmit power for

the m^{th} subcarrier using modulation order M_m , H_m is the observed subchannel gain, S_m is the PU Power Spectral Density (PSD), and $I(P(M_m, H_m, S_m))$ is the resultant interference power observed by the PU due to the m^{th} subcarrier power level. Note that $M_m = 1$ is introduced in (6) to account for *unused* subcarriers, as identified by zero entries in SMSE variable \mathbf{u} in (1), with $P(M_m, H_m, S_m) \equiv 0$ when $M_m = 1$.

Additional gains can be obtained by adapting to the PU temporal responses as well. This can be achieved by monitoring the PU transmissions and keeping track of the current “state” of each PU transmitter. This information can then be used to update the expected number of PU signals that will be transmitted during the next SMSE symbol interval. As a result, the expected amount of PU power that will interfere with the SMSE signal, as well as the expected number of PU signals that will experience interference from the SMSE signal, can be estimated. The OFDM subcarrier response can then be designed accordingly, enabling the SMSE system to vary its subcarrier selection, modulation, and power on a symbol-by-symbol basis, or as often as is needed and practical.

The PU signal “state” can be interpreted in numerous ways. In general, the “state” description includes any information that the SMSE system has and can maintain about PU transmission characteristics. If the PU signals are transmitted as bursts having fixed time duration or fixed guard intervals between bursts, this information can be included as part of the “state” description and used to compute times that the PU is most likely to transmit. Alternatively, in the simplest “on-off” model, the PU “state” can be modeled simply as whether or not the PU was transmitting at the end of the most recent OFDM symbol. In this case, the expectation that a PU signal will begin transmitting can be computed statistically by observing PU transmissions for a defined period of time. In this simplified situation, the SMSE system builds a model estimate of PU signal statistics and tailors its temporal response accordingly. The SMSE system can maintain updated PU statistics and alter its behavior when PU signal statistics change.

Accounting for temporal PU signal characteristics, the SMSE design constraints in (6) through (8) become:

$$\underset{M_m=\{1,4,16,64,256\}}{\text{Max}} \left\{ \sum_{m=0}^{N_f-1} \log_2(M_m) \right\}, \quad (9)$$

such that

$$\mathbf{E} \left\{ \sum_{m=0}^{N_f-1} P(M_m, H_m, S_m) \right\} \leq P_T, \quad (10)$$

$$\mathbf{E} \left\{ \sum_{m=0}^{N_f-1} I(P(M_m, H_m, S_m)) \right\} \leq I_T, \quad (11)$$

where $\mathbf{E}\{\bullet\}$ denotes expected value across all possible PU states. As before, these equations can be solved using Lagrange’s method. The resultant OFDM signal is now designed to fill both spectral and temporal “voids” and avoids areas of significant PU power as well as low channel gain.

IV. TIME-FREQUENCY POWER DISTRIBUTION

Considering only spectral adaptation constraints, the signal satisfying (6) through (8) is able to avoid spectral areas of significant PU power as well as low channel gain while maximizing its throughput. This is illustrated in the time-frequency PSD responses shown in Fig 1 for a representative optimization scenario. In this case, the SMSE system is operating in a multipath fading environment and spectrally adapts to four spectrally separated DSSS PU signals transmitting in burst mode. The resultant *spectrally adapted* SMSE signal response (middle plot of Fig 1) clearly avoids the spectral areas occupied by the DSSS PU signals.

Considering both spectral and temporal adaptation constraints, the signal satisfying (9) through (11) is able to avoid spectral and temporal areas of significant PU power as well as low channel response regions while maximizing its throughput. This is illustrated in the time-frequency PSD responses shown in Fig 2, where the adapted SMSE signal spectrally and temporally avoids the four DSSS PU signals using the simple “on-off” state model. The resultant *spectrally-temporally adapted* SMSE signal response (middle plot of Fig 2) has a distinct response that effectively power fills “voids” around the DSSS PU signals in both time and frequency. The SMSE response clearly avoids spectral areas where the DSSS signals are actually present.

V. BIT ERROR RATE AND THROUGHPUT

SMSE system performance is simulated in a coexistent environment containing four DSSS PU signals. The

Fig. 1. *Spectrally Adapted* coexistent PSDs: (Top) Four *DSSS* PU Signals, (Middle) Adapted *SMSE* Signal and (Bottom) *Combined* *DSSS* and *SMSE* signals.

Fig. 2. *Spectrally-Temporally Adapted* coexistent PSDs: (Top) Four *DSSS* PU Signals, (Middle) Adapted *SMSE* Signal and (Bottom) *Combined* *DSSS* and *SMSE* signals.

DSSS PU signals use Binary Phase Shift Keyed (BPSK) modulation for both data and spreading. The transmitted PU power level is fixed at 20 Watts per PU using a symbol rate of 300K Sym/Sec. An Additive White Gaussian Noise (AWGN) channel is used with a power spectral density of $N_0/2 = 4 \times 10^{-6}$ Watts/Hz. A 32-length Hadamard sequence is used for the spreading code with exactly one code period per BPSK data symbol. The four PU signals are spectrally non-overlapped at center frequencies of 2.0120 GHz, 2.0383 GHz, 2.0680 GHz, and 2.0931 GHz. Each PU signal is generated using independent data modulation, carrier phase and symbol timing. The PU signals are burst transmissions and are modeled using an exponential random variable with a mean duration of 20.0 mSec for both burst length and burst separation. The SMSE signal uses a maximum of $N_f = 8192$ possible subcarriers that are confined to a frequency band of 2.000 GHz to 2.105 GHz (105 MHz maximum bandwidth). Each subcarrier experiences independent Rayleigh flat fading through the AWGN channel. Furthermore, all transmitters and receivers in the scenario (PU and SMSE) are assumed to observe the same set of signals, but independent noise realizations.

Simulated PU and SMSE BER performance is shown in Fig 3 for the spectrally-only designed SMSE waveform, and the spectrally-temporally designed SMSE waveform. For comparison, SMSE performance is also presented without the DSSS PU signals present. Consider-

ing the SMSE BER curves (filled symbols), the SMSE BER is shown to meet the desired BER limit of $P_B = 10^{-4}$ for the entire range of SMSE transmit power limits simulated, with all three curves overlapping. Considering the PU BER curves (unfilled symbols) as the SMSE transmit power limit increases, the PU BER increases up to within a factor of $\pm 10\%$ of the maximum BER constraint of $P_B = 10^{-4}$. For lower SMSE power levels the PU BER is substantially lower than the BER limit. This occurs because the SMSE signal is able to select sub-carrier frequencies that are considerably removed from the DSSS PU spectral regions and apply maximum power levels without causing significant interference to the PU systems.

Simulated results in Fig 4 show average SMSE bit rate (throughput) versus total maximum SMSE power (normalized by the maximum SMSE bandwidth of 105 MHz) for both the *spectrally adapted* and *spectrally-temporally adapted* waveforms. Performance without DSSS PU signals present is also provided for comparison. For the lower maximum total power limits considered, all three systems performed nearly identically. This occurs because the SMSE system can allocate its total power to very few high gain channels. Therefore, when the DSSS PU signals are present, the SMSE design is effectively a simple frequency division multiplexing scheme that avoids sub-channels with high interference. Since there are generally enough high gain

Fig. 3. Coexistent BER for the adapted SMSE signal (Filled Symbols) and DSSS PUs (Unfilled Symbols) using a BER limit constraint of $P_B = 10^{-4}$ for both systems.

Fig. 4. Simulated SMSE bit rate (throughput) versus total maximum SMSE power (normalized by the maximum SMSE bandwidth) using a BER limit constraint of $P_B = 10^{-4}$ for both systems.

channels outside the DSSS PU spectral regions, the SMSE system experiences minimal penalty for avoiding the DSSS PU sub-bands. However, as total available power increases the SMSE system begins to share DSSS PU sub-channels and realizes a noticeable performance improvement.

VI. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

Efficient use of channel resources has been demonstrated for a coexistent SMSE-DSSS PU scenario. Results in Fig. 3 demonstrate that the OFDM-based SMSE design procedure is effective given that BER constraints were satisfied to within a factor of approximately 10%. Relative to a signal that has only been adapted spectrally, SMSE bit rate (throughput) results in Fig. 4 show that for higher total power limits there is an approximate 20% increase in throughput, or approximately 18M Bits/Sec, using a spectrally-temporally adapted signal. For these higher SMSE power limits, the OFDM-based SMSE signal realizes approximately 85% of the bit rate achievable when there are no DSSS PU signals present.

Results highlight the potential for considerable performance improvement by varying both the spectral and temporal and behavior of the adapted signal. This is demonstrated here in a coexistent environment using an OFDM-based SMSE signal with subcarrier power and modulation order independently adapted on an intra-symbol basis. The coexistent scenario included the adaptive SMSE signal and four coexistent DSSS primary users. Using knowledge of PU spectral and temporal transmission characteristics, the OFDM-based SMSE signal was effectively adapted to maximize its own bit rate while maintaining imposed BER constraints on coexisting PU signals. It is envisioned that the required PU knowledge could be based on either a priori knowledge of the environment or by observing the statistical behavior of the coexistent environment over time.

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REFERENCES

- [1] P. Mannion, “Sharing spectrum the smarter way,” *EE Times*, April 2004.
- [2] I. Akyildiz, W. Lee, M. Vuren, and S. Mohanty, “NeXt Gen / DSA / CR Wireless Networks: A Survey,” *Elsevier Computer Networks*, vol. 50, May 2006.
- [3] N. Devroye and P. Mitran, “Achievable rates in cr channels,” *IEEE Trans on Information Theory*, vol. 52, no. 5, May 2006.
- [4] S. Haykin, “Cognitive radio: Brain-empowered wireless communications,” vol. 23, no. 2, pp. 201–220, Feb. 2005.
- [5] A. R. S. Bahai and B. R. Saltzberg, *Multi-Carrier Digital Communications: Theory and Applications of OFDM*. Norwell, MA: Kluwer, 1999.
- [6] R. G. Gallager, *Information Theory and Reliable Communication*. New York: Wiley, 1999.
- [7] M. E. Haker, “Hardware realization of a transform domain communication,” Master’s thesis, Air Force Institute of Technology, Wright-Patterson AFB OH, March 2007.
- [8] *IEEE Std for Info Tech–Telecom and Info Exchange Between Systems (LANs/MANs)– Specific Requirements Part 11: Wireless LAN MAC and PHY Specss*, IEEE Computer Society, 2007.
- [9] S. Honda, D. Umehara, T. Hayasaki, S. Denno, and M. Morikura, “A fast bit loading algorithm synchronized with commercial power supply for in-home plc systems,” in *IEEE Int’l Sym on Power Line Comm & Apps*, April 2008.
- [10] D. Hughes-Hartogs, “Ensemble modem structure for imperfect transmission media,” U.S. Patent # 4,731,816, March 1988.
- [11] B. S. Krongold, K. Ramchandran, and D. L. Jones, “Computationally efficient optimal power allocation algorithms for MC comm sys,” *IEEE Trans on Comm*, vol. 48, no. 1, 2000.
- [12] Z. Hu, G. Zhu, Y. Xia, and G. Liu, “Multiuser subcarrier and bit allocation for MIMO-OFDM systems,” in *IEEE Wireless Comm and Net Conf*, vol. 2, March 2004.
- [13] J. Jang, K. B. Lee, , and Y.-H. Lee, “Transmit power and bit allocations for ofdm systems in a fading channel,” in *IEEE IEEE Global Telecommunications Conference*, 2003.
- [14] S. Ye, R. Blum, and J. Cimini, L.J., “Adaptive modulation for variable-rate ofdm systems with imperfect channel information,” in *IEEE Vehicular Technology Conference*, 2002.
- [15] C. Y. Wong, R. S. Cheng, K. B. Letaief, and R. D. Murch, “Multiuser ofdm with adaptive subcarrier, bit and power allocation,” *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas of Communications*, vol. 17, October 1999.
- [16] M. L. Roberts, M. A. Temple, M. E. Oxley, R. F. Mills, and R. A. Raines, “A general analytic framework for spectrally modulated, spectrally encoded signals,” in *IEEE International Conference on Waveform Diversity and Design*, January 2006.
- [17] M. L. Roberts, M. A. Temple, R. F. Mills, and R. A. Raines, “Communication waveform design using an adaptive smse framework,” *IEEE Journal on Selected Topics in Signal Processing*, vol. 1, no. 1, June 2007.
- [18] —, “Interference suppression characterization for smse signals,” *IEEE Electronic Letters*, vol. 42, no. 19, September 2006.
- [19] M. L. Roberts, M. A. Temple, M. E. Oxley, R. F. Mills, and R. A. Raines, “An Analytic SMSE framework for CI signals,” in *ACM Intl Wireless Commun and Mobile Computing Conf*.